

ARTS

MODERN - TEST METHODS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

This article deals with the issues of integration in the process of visual activity. In this regard, color test models are offered in a table consisting of cross (cube sweep) figures, as well as ornaments. Such tests can become significant for the development of interdisciplinary connections with such subjects as drawing, geometry, fine arts, color science, psychology (logical thinking), etc. This, in turn, will provide a modern and integrative approach to the educational process in fine arts.

Keywords: fine arts, design, thinking, testing, integrative approach

Introduction

Fine arts studied in secondary and special higher educational institutions provide the assimilation of skills and knowledge in artistic activity, and also develops artistic and aesthetic thinking and aesthetic worldview of subjects. Along with this, this item forms the right aesthetic attitude to the environment.

Methodology

It should be noted that for the formation of all these qualities in the subject of fine arts, it is necessary to carefully and comprehensively study the physical properties and psychological effects of colors[3], as well as the shapes and structures of various figures (especially geometric figures and bodies) and objects[1;2;4;5]. In connection with this issue, various methods and approaches are used in the process of teaching relevant subjects. At the present stage, test methods are also widely used in this direction.

Main part

When compiling logical tests, unlike colors, graphic images based on various shapes, symbols and other elements are used more. However, it should be borne in mind that in logical tests, due to multidimensional properties, the use of colors would be more effective in a comprehensive study and study of the subject. As you know, different colors and their shades affect the psycho-emotional state of a person, and they are perceived at different levels.

Color tests, consisting of geometric shapes, are especially important for students and students involved in fine arts. They can also be used to determine logical,

artistic thinking, as well as the development of aesthetic taste, visual (visual) perception and the correct approach to a compositional solution. The creation and application of such tests can be based on the multidimensional features of colors and in this context express the essence and content of the task in an integrative form (both in figures and in colors).

Findings

It should be noted that the use of such test methods (in secondary and special higher educational institutions) can provide and strengthen interdisciplinary links between such subjects as drawing, geometry, fine arts, color science, psychology (logical thinking), etc. This, in turn, will provide a modern integrative approach to the educational process.

Examples of test tasks.

Task No. 1 (*fig.1, a, c*). The maximum number of cross figures (cube sweep) can be cut in the table.

A. - 4; **B.** - 5; **C.** - 9; **D.** - 10.

Task No. 2 (*fig. 2, a, c*). How many cross figures (unfolding of the cube) will fit in the table symmetrically in color and arrangement of the figures.

A. - 6; **B.** - 8; **C.** - 10; **D.** - 12.

Task No. 3 (*fig. 3*). How many variants of the cube expansion exist in the table?

A. - e, f, c, o; **B.** - a, b, h, q; **C.** - e, f, n, q; **D.** - c, m, o, p.

Task No. 4 (*fig. 4*). For symmetry, which figures should be rotated in the table?

A. - 4 - 11; **B.** - 10-11; **C.** - 12-13; **D.** - 11-16.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								

a

	a		b		c		d	
a	a	a	b	c	c	c	d	
	a	b	b	b	c	d	d	d
	a	e	b	f	c	g	d	
e	e	e	e	f	g	g	g	g
	h	e	f	f	f	g	i	
h	h	h	h	f	i	i	i	i
	h						i	

c

Fig.1 (a, c)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								

a

	a			b		c		
a	a	a	a	b	c	c	c	c
	a	d	b	b	b	e	c	
d	d	d	d	b	e	e	e	e
	f	d				e	g	
f	f	f	f		g	g	g	g
	f	h				i	g	
h	h	h	h	k	i	i	i	i
	j	h	k	k	k	i	l	
j	j	j	j	k	l	l	l	l
	j			k			l	

c

Fig.2 (a, c)

	a	b	b	b	c	d	d	
a	a	a	b	b	c	d	d	d
e	a	a	b	c	c	g	g	d
e	e	e	e	f	c	g	g	g
h	h	h	e	f	c	g	k	k
h	h	i	f	f	f	k	k	k
h	i	i	i	f	l	l	m	k
n	i	i	l	l	l	l	m	o
n	n	n	n	m	m	m	m	o
p	p	n	q	q	q	o	o	o
p	p	p	p		q	q	q	o

Fig.3

Fig.4

Right answers:

- Task No. 1. - **C**;
- Task No. 2. - **D**;
- Task No. 3. - **C**;
- Task No. 4. - **A**;

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